

Description of Implemented Data App Algorithms

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the algorithms underlying the data apps defined in D1.1 [1] and whose results are reported in D3.1 [2]. While D3.1 answers the question of what the data apps produced, this deliverable addresses how those results were obtained, documenting methodological approaches, design choices, and algorithmic dependencies among the apps. Only the apps chosen for development are shown. The choice of developed apps is based on their feasibility within the project's timeframe. Transparent algorithm documentation is relevant not only to DSOs seeking to operationalise these tools but also to researchers, electricians, and engineers who may wish to reproduce or adapt the methods in their own contexts. The descriptions are kept at a high methodological level; code-level implementation details are available in the open-source repository on GitHub.

The presented apps have been categorised into three main groups, the first group comprising data apps that are particularly for data preparation and topology refinement, thereby setting the stage for their usability in other data apps. These apps include the data extractor - for timeseries data loading and topology refinement, SM classifier for characterisation and classification of smart meters, SM phase mapper for refining per-phase topology information and mapping SMs based on their voltage measurements, and data corrector serving as a data updating patch, particularly for cleaning SM profiles, phase correction, and topology cleaner. The second category contains data apps for phase imbalance analytics. Hence, the phase imbalance profiler and phase imbalance analyser have been presented. The last category covers apps that help identify electrification loads and the phases they are connected to. In this case, the focus was on identifying electrical heating, electric vehicles, and photovoltaic panels. For the group of electrification loads, a data app for Phase connector assistance is added that was not in D3.1 [2], which is used as an endpoint for a service described in D4.1 [3].

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1 Introduction

1.1 Project background

The rapid electrification of the grid is placing more pressure on distribution networks, where increasing numbers of heat pumps, electric vehicles (EVs), and other power electronic devices introduce additional loads and often phase imbalance. At the same time, Danish distribution system operators (DSOs) generally lack detailed observability of low-voltage (LV) grids: topology records might have errors, phase-connection information is often dependent on the communication form of the meters and missing for some meters, and power quality monitoring is limited or absent at secondary substations. This lack of granular, per-phase visibility forces DSOs to rely on conservative planning assumptions, leading to unnecessary capacity buffers, delayed customer connections, and costly reinforcement measures that slow down the green transition.

Motivated by these challenges, the 3PhaseInsight project unlocks the value of per-phase smart-meter measurements by developing advanced analytics and scalable data-processing pipelines. The platform validates on a dataset of around 100,000 customers provided by Radius, a leading DSO in Denmark, demonstrating real-world performance at scale and establishing a proven foundation for broader deployment. The central idea is that modern smart meters can provide per-phase voltage, power, and harmonic information at a granularity that enables a new level of LV situational awareness. The platform delivers actionable insights through state-of-the-art data-driven and machine-learning algorithms, directly supporting more efficient operation, planning, and stakeholder-level data sharing.

Building on this foundation, Work Package 3 develops and evaluates a set of modular Data Apps that transform three-phase smart-meter measurements into actionable knowledge. These apps are designed to identify topology inconsistencies, quantify phase imbalance, and detect significant electrification loads through scalable data-processing pipelines.

Deliverable D3.1 [2] documented the results obtained from these apps, including their outputs, example visualisations, key insights, and scaling behaviour. This deliverable complements the results by documenting the algorithms underlying them. That is, D3.1 answers the question of what the Data Apps produced, while this document (D3.2) addresses how those results were obtained. To avoid repetition, this document will partially include results from data apps by leaving detailed descriptions in D3.1 and instead focus on methodological approaches, design choices, and algorithmic dependencies between apps.

1.2 Scope

This deliverable covers the selected Data Apps that reached sufficient maturity and are reported in D3.1. These include apps for data preparation and topology refinement, imbalance analytics, and detection of significant electrification loads. The descriptions are intentionally kept at a high methodological level: enough detail is provided to explain the implemented logic and justify the algorithmic choices, but code-level implementation details are to be detailed in the proceeding deliverables. The description also reflects the project's practical emphasis on algorithms that are interpretable, reproducible, and suitable for later integration into modular open-source data-pipeline solutions. The presented methodologies and figures are based on the local prototyping environment described in D2.2 [4] to maintain consistency with D3.1 [2]. Any considerable changes made for the open source platform will be described in D4.1 [3]

2 Methodological approaches by functional area

2.1 Smart meter data preparation and quality enhancement

2.1.1 Data Extractor

The Data Extractor is the data backbone of the project, by standardizing input data and providing a unified interface for loading, transforming, storing raw- and processed topology and time-series data, so that all data applications use the same format data.

Methodology: The Data extractor consist of a customizable sequence of data-preparation tasks, for data-formats described more in detail in D2.2 [4]. In broad strokes, the preparation algorithms can be descried as:

1. **Load raw topology and smart meter data:** Load source CSV data provided by the DSO, including monthly time-series measurements, topology data, and meter and cabinet connection tables.
2. **Create topology mappings:** Build hierarchical mappings that connect each smart meter to the network structure (Cabinet → Feeder → Transformer → Secondary Substation → ZIP code), and optionally the reversed mapping from smart meter to location.
3. **Extract data for individual smart meters:** Extract profiles for selected smart meters. Since this is typically the most computationally expensive step, it is often beneficial to extract all smart meters once and store per-smart meter profile Parquet files for reuse.
4. **Optional: use cleaned/ phase corrected inputs:** If available, use cleaned, phase corrected or cleaned-and-phase-corrected datasets from the dedicated cleaning/correction apps (see Section 2.1.4) before downstream extraction.
5. **Optional: add derived features:** During extraction, optionally compute derived variables such as phase current and phase-imbalance indicators.
6. **Aggregate by network category:** Return bundled datasets for downstream apps that operate on groups of meters, including:
 - Per_Smart_Meter
 - Per_Cabinet
 - Per_Feeder
 - Per_Transformer
 - Per_Secondary_Substation
 - Per_ZIP_Code
 - All HP meters
 - All PV meters
7. **Return or save requested output:** Return data in memory for immediate use or save as Parquet files for reproducible and efficient downstream processing.

Approach: The Data extractor is used in every other data app to query results and and is therefore very broad and modular to accommodate different data needs as they arrived.

Take-away and Limitations: The Data extractor provides a highly modularized way of creating exactly the data needed for a given data app. The method described here works very well for local development, however for the cloud based platform described in D4.1 [3] the architecture had to be changed somewhat while the core features stayed the same, these changes is described in [3].

2.1.2 Smart Meter Classifier

Smart Meter Classifier categorically goes over smart meters time-series data, and generates general classifications and characterizations using arithmetic methods.

Characterization contains per-smart meter informations such as topology connection, quality classes measurements and derived features such as percentage of corrupted, frozen or missing data for every investigated smart meter. *Classifications* contains summarized listed information, such as data quality and availability for all investigated smart meters. Contents in the characterization and classification dictionaries are listed in the D3.1 [2].

Methodology: Individual or multiple smart meters can be evaluated at once using Smart Meter Classifier. The data app loads a raw or processed topology mapping from Data Extractor and iteratively goes over each injected smart meter ID, loads time-series data, determine its topology structure and fills a classification and characteristic dictionary using arithmetic methods.

- **Diagnosing topology:** A Topology mapping is called using Data Extractor in a dictionary format. The associated cabinet ID, feeder ID, transformer ID, and secondary substation ID for each smart meter ID is located. This information is subsequently being injected in the characterization dictionary per smart meter ID.
- **Connectional assessment:** Phases from smart meters are characterized as connected if the number of timestamps with data exceed a pre-specified limit. A phase is characterized as having a connection error if the ratio between the phase voltage mean and the phase offset voltage mean, i.e. if the phase has an unhealthy voltage at $230 \pm 10\%$, is above a pre-specified offset-threshold. A phase is characterized as having a switching phase, if the phase has a varying consumption pattern with a pre-specified number of timestamps with data, then followed by the same number of timestamps with no data.
- **Data quality evaluations:** Phases from smart meters are iteratively examined on the voltage, active power and reactive power. Depending on user pre-specified thresholds, the units are characterized as *good*, *medium*, or *bad* if the time stamps with data exceed the thresholds. A classified good voltage, could be a voltage, where there are more than 90% time stamps with data, while a medium voltage could be above 50%. A bad voltage is classified otherwise. Details on the ratio of missing values, number of frozen recordings, number of voltage points and under the offset threshold, and the total ratio of corrupted (either one of these categories), are added to the data quality evaluation.
- **Statistical summaries:** Phases from smart meters are iteratively examined on the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation on the voltage, active power and reactive power.
- **Rule-based classification:** A dictionary is initiated for all the injected smart meters, and the classifications keys are iteratively filled. Some keys are directly filled from results of the characterization dictionary, such as the data availability, while others are derived based on these results, such as the number of connected phases.

Approach: The Smart Meter Classifier is used on an ingested list of smart meters ID, or 'all', which covers all smart meters IDs of a specific data batch. For each run with a unique run-result name, it produces classification and characterization dictionaries under this a folder with this name. Smart

Meter Phase Mapper and Data Corrector, as a part of their code, also uses this Smart Meter Classifier - primarily for its characterization dictionary due to its content of lists of unconnected smart meter phases.

Take-away: The Smart Meter Classifier classifies and characterizes smart meters and their phases, and collects the results into two dictionaries. The characterizations contain details on topology, connections, data quality and statistics *per* investigated smart meter phases, whereas the classification contains summaries of results from the characterization, including categories such as data containment, data classes (good, medium, bad), connections, and switching and connection classes for *all* investigated smart meters.

2.1.3 Smart Meter Phase Mapper

Smart Meter Phase Mapper refines existing per-phase topology information by examining all smart meter phase-voltage measurements within a transformer and grouping them by profile similarity. Phases that are electrically close are typically supplied by the same transformer phase (I1, I2, I3) and feeder, and exhibit higher correlations. Using *agglomerative hierarchical clustering* with complete linkage and Spearman correlation-based distance metric, phases from a transformer can be mapped, and phase twist, double-connection, wrongful allocated feeders, transformer or cabinet units in existing topology mappings can be updated.

Methodology Smart Meter Phase Mapper compares the per-smart meter phase voltage correlation between all smart meter phases within a transformer.

- **Pre-processing smart meter phases:** By ingesting transformer IDs, associated smart meter IDs are found using raw or processed topology mapping. Characterizations are found from these smart meter IDs using the Smart Meter Classifier, which can reveal unconnected phases. Using Data Extractor, per-phase smart meter voltage data associated to the transformer ID is queried to a dataframe. The frame is cleaned by dropping unconnected phases and phases with a constant voltage offset ($230V \pm 10\%$).
- **Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering** The dataframe is differentiated to remove trends and ensure stationarity, then standardized to zero mean and unit variance, before a distance matrix is created based on Spearman correlation. Based on the distance matrix, a complete linkage matrix is generated.
- **Pre-cluster evaluation:** The linkage matrix is partitioned into three flat clusters, representing each phase. At each internal node within these, a new cluster is accepted as a *feeder-phase cluster* if a clear majority feeder ($\geq 75\%$ of phases) and a clear majority phase label ($\geq 58\%$) can be identified, and if minority-feeder phases are distributed across both sub-clusters rather than isolated in one branch. The linkage tree is traversed iteratively from root to leaves until all phases (leaves) are placed in a *feeder-phase cluster*.
- **Label consistency:** A potential wrong feeder detection from the pre-cluster evaluation is only confirmed if all uncorrupted phases of the same smart meter report the same feeder discrepancy. Since a physically misallocated meter will have all its phases routed through the wrong feeder, a discrepancy appearing on only a subset of phases is attributed to a phase twist rather than a feeder misallocation. The confirmed wrong feeder labels are passed into a second, final cluster evaluation.
- **Classifying evaluation** Accepted clusters are examined for four topology classes: *SM phase twists*, where a smart meter's reported phase label disagrees with the cluster majority, *wrong feeder labels*, where a smart meter's reported feeder ID disagrees with the cluster majority, *double*

connections, where a smart meter appears more than once within the same feeder-phase cluster, and *wrong transformer assignments*, where an isolated cluster consists exclusively of phases from a single smart meter, suggesting it belongs to a different transformer. Else, a phase is considered *normal*. If a node does not satisfy the acceptance criteria, the algorithm descends into its two constituent sub-clusters and repeats the evaluation, continuing until all phases are assigned to a feeder-phase cluster.

Approach: The Smart Meter Classifier is used on an ingested list of transformer ID, or 'all', which covers all transformer IDs of a specific data batch. For each run with a unique run-result name it produces a CSV, listing all the smart meter phases associated with the transformer IDs from the injected list, their existing topology information (affiliated cabinets, feeders) and the class from the Smart Meter Phase Mapper evaluation. Besides this, it also produces a SVG image of the hierarchical structure for each transformer, showcasing the phase-feeder relation through the correlation based distance. Data Corrector uses the Smart Meter Phase Mapper results to update the existing topology information based on derived classes.

Take-away: The Smart Meter Phase Mapper refines existing per-phase topology information using hierarchical clustering and rule-based and heuristic methods. Each smart meter phase, from an investigated transformer ID, has its topology evaluated based on the voltage profile similarity to their providing feeder. If insufficient correlation is found, the smart meter phase can be put into different classes: "wrong feeder", "wrong transformer", "phase twist", "unconnected", "doubled-phased" or "unknown". The results are described more in detail in D3.1 [2].

Figure 1: Plotted unspecified smart meter ID with only good quality. All phases are plotted with sub-figures for the voltage, active power, and reactive power.

2.1.4 Data Corrector

Data Corrector corrects the existing time-series and topology data, depended on results derived from either Smart Meter Phase Mapper or Smart Meter Classifier, and produces new corrected data based

on algorithms from four sub-modules. The corrected newly produced data is inferred as being either *cleaned* or *phase corrected*.

The four modules are as follows:

- **Smart Meter Profile Cleaner**
- **Smart Meter Phase Corrector**
- **Topology Cleaner**
- **Topology Phase Corrector**

As these have a high degree of dependence, they are described together below

Methodology

- **Rule-based smart meter profile cleaning:** *Smart Meter Profile Cleaner* corrects data per smart meter by first loading the phase characterization results from Smart Meter Classifier. Phases classified as *unconnected* or *switching* are dropped, while phases with a *connection error* are corrected by shifting their voltage profile to align with the median of neighbouring phases on the same feeder. Neighbouring smart meters from the feeder are found using either existing topology, or results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper.

For the remaining smart meter phases, offset voltage values ($230V \pm 10\%$) and frozen signals (same value for a pre-specified number of consecutive time stamps), are flagged as missing. A regression model (*LightGBM*) is then trained on available data using neighbouring smart meter measurements on the same feeder, rolling statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis), and calendar features (time of day, day of year) as input. Where phase mapping results are available from Smart Meter Phase Mapper, twisted phases in the neighbour set are relabelled to their correct phase prior to model training, ensuring that only electrically comparable signals are used as regressors. Remaining outliers are detected by applying a rolling IQR-based whisker criterion to the absolute error between the raw signal and the model prediction, and both missing and outlier values are replaced with the model predictions.

Cleaned and imputed data is stored as *cleaned* data.

- **Phase correcting and combining cleaned data:** *Smart Meter Phase Corrector* applies the topology corrections from Smart Meter Phase Mapper directly to the per-smart meter profile datasets, relabelling phase columns to reflect their true electrical connection. For each smart meter phase, the corrected label is determined by a configurable reference hierarchy. If *feeder-phase twists* are considered, the transformer phase is used as the primary reference, falling back to the feeder phase if the transformer phase is unavailable. If feeder-phase twists are not considered, the feeder phase is used directly. A phase column is only renamed if its reported label disagrees with the reference. Smart meters flagged as containing *doubled-phased* connections are optionally included, in which case the two columns mapping to the same phase are combined by averaging voltage columns and summarizing active and reactive power columns. Phases flagged as *unconnected* are left unlabelled. Phase corrected is stored as *phase corrected* data, or *cleaned and phase corrected* if the analysed smart meter data is cleaned using *Smart Meter Profile Cleaner*.

- **Clean existing topology:** *Topology Cleaner* cleans existing topology files by imputing missing data. Two files are cleaned, which of both are described in detail in D3.1 [2]; topology- and meter and cabinet data.

For the topology file, missing values in the cable capacity, cable length, phase size, resistance, reactance, and feeder fuse size columns, are imputed first by the mean of the respective substation, falling back to the global mean if all values within a substation are missing. The assumption of

duplicate cable entries between the same pair of nodes are resolved by retaining only the entry with the highest current-carrying capacity.

For the meter and cabinet file, rows where the meter number is missing are removed, as these correspond to cabinets with no smart meter attached.

- **Producing cleaned and corrected topology:** *Topology Phase Corrector* corrects existing topology files using results from Smart Meter Phase Mapper and the cleaned topology files from *Topology Cleaner*.

The meter and cabinet file is updated by identifying all smart meters flagged with a *Wrong Feeder* status and reassigning their cabinet entry to the likely cabinet identified by the phase mapper, thereby correcting their feeder allocation in the topology. The Topology file is retained as cleaned, as no cable-level corrections are derived from the phase mapping results. The corrected files are stored as *cleaned and phase corrected*.

Approach: The 4 sub-modules are closely connected.

To obtain *cleaned and phase corrected* time-series data, *Smart Meter Profile Cleaner* must be executed before *Smart Meter Phase Corrector*. To obtain any one of *cleaned* or *phase corrected* time-series data, the apps can be used independently of each other.

This exact pipeline also holds true for *Topology Cleaner* and *Topology Phase Corrector*.

The time-series data depend on profile-level data, which is queried using Data Extractor.

Take-away: A *cleaned, phase corrected* or combined *cleaned and phase corrected* processing level can be obtained for both smart meter time-series data and topology data using the 4 Data Corrector sub-modules. *Cleaned* refers to the data being imputed for missing or noisy values, and empty or faulty dataframe columns of data values begin removed. *Phase corrected* refers to data being corrected based on results of phase-feeder or phase-transformer connections inferred from Smart Meter Phase Mapper.

Using either one of the modules generates processed data and saves the files in a local separate folder. In the open-source platform, *cleaned* and *phase corrected* flags are added to the time-series data to avoid saving duplicate data. When processed time-series data is requested, real-time computations of imputing missing and correcting labels, are executed on raw data. This is explained more in detail in D2.2 [4].

2.2 Phase imbalance assessment and power flow analysis

Phase imbalance assessment and power flow analysis is a pipeline of data apps with a 3-phase unbalanced power flow as the base to be able to analyse the imbalance of buses and lines/cables for diagnostics. The Data apps take elements from and build upon the work by David B. Andreasen [5] and Jason A. Quinn [6].

2.2.1 Power Flow Tool

The Power Flow Tool constructs a per-substation network model from the data extracted by the Data Extractor and uses PandaPower [7] to execute a three-phase unbalanced power flow.¹ The following paragraphs describe the methodology in the network construction, load modelling, and power flow execution in detail.

¹In the dataset used here, only one transformer was measured per substation. If more than one transformer exists per substation, each should be examined individually; this can be configured in the code by adjusting the config file.

Network Construction A PandaPower network is built from the topology data delivered by the Data Extractor. Each connection points in the topology, cabinets, feeders, and similar, is represented as a bus, while cables between them are represented as three-phase lines. Positive and negative sequence parameters are given in the topology (resistance R , reactance X), but zero sequence parameters and capacitance is defined as in [5]. Additionally the transformers are all assumed to be Delta-Wye as per the DSO [8]. The low-voltage (LV) network operates at a base voltage of 0.4 kV. A slack bus is placed on the medium-voltage (MV) side of the substation transformer, set to 10 kV, representing the upstream grid connection and providing the voltage reference for the power flow solution.

Load and Generation Modelling Measured loads and distributed generation (e.g. PV) are mapped to their corresponding buses via the network topology. Two injection modes are supported:

- **Separate injection:** Active and reactive power for consumption and generation are injected as distinct PandaPower load and static generator elements, respectively. This preserves the sign and physical interpretation of each device
- **Net injection:** Consumption and generation at each bus are summed before injection, yielding a single net power value per phase per bus. This reduces model complexity and is appropriate when only aggregate measurements are available or when computational speed is a priority.

In both modes, power is injected per phase, preserving any asymmetry present in the measured data and allowing the unbalanced power flow to capture phase-level effects.

Power Flow Execution An asymmetric three-phase power flow is solved using the Newton–Raphson method with a flat start (all bus voltages initialised to 1 p.u. and 0°). The Newton–Raphson iteration proceeds until the maximum residual in the power mismatch vector falls below the convergence tolerance, ensuring a consistent solution across all phases simultaneously. The primary outputs of the power flow are per-phase bus voltages, per-phase line currents, and active and reactive power losses for each cable segment, which are stored and passed downstream for further analysis.

In addition to the unbalanced power flow, a *balanced* power flow variant is also available. In the balanced case, the total three-phase power at each bus is redistributed equally across the three phases before injection, representing the theoretical scenario in which loads are perfectly balanced. This balanced reference case is used by the Phase Imbalance Profiler (Section 2.2.2) to quantify the impact of existing imbalance on cable loading and network losses.

Approach The Power Flow Tool is the central groundwork of the phase analysis pipeline. It sits between the Data Extractor, which supplies topology and measurements, and the downstream analysis tools, primarily the Phase Imbalance Profiler, which applies the power flow results. By running a separate power flow for each substation, the tool scales naturally to networks with many substations and isolates convergence issues to individual substations without affecting the rest of the run. Both the balanced and unbalanced power flows are executed across the full measurement time series, producing a per-timestep result set that downstream tools aggregate into statistics and visualisations.

Limitations and Take-away The results produced by the Power Flow Tool are *model-based estimates*, not direct measurements. The accuracy of the estimated voltages, currents, and losses therefore depends on the fidelity of the network model, and in particular on three main sources of uncertainty: (i) the sequence impedance parameters, which are taken from tabulated reference values rather than field measurements; (ii) the topology, which is assumed to be accurately represented in the dataset; and (iii) the load and generation time series, which reflect the measurement uncertainty of the smart meters and loss of information in the 15-minute granularity. Users should interpret quantitative results in light of these modelling assumptions

Figure 2: Example of line loading for all buses in a substation over a select data period, as an intermediate result

Figure 3: Voltage per unit for all busses in a substation over a select data period, as a intermediate result

2.2.2 Phase Imbalance Profiler

The Phase Imbalance Profiler takes the output from the power flow simulation to compute imbalance-specific metrics, derive capacity and loss impact estimates, and visualise results on a topology map. The following subsections describe each part of the methodology in detail.

Voltage Unbalance Factor (VUF) The Voltage Unbalance Factor (VUF) is an established and regulated voltage-quality metric that characterises the degree of asymmetry in a three-phase voltage system. Voltage unbalance degrades the performance of rotating machinery, increases losses in induction motors, and can cause nuisance tripping of sensitive equipment. VUF is defined via the method of symmetrical components as the ratio of the negative-sequence voltage magnitude to the positive-sequence voltage magnitude, expressed as a percentage:

$$\text{VUF} [\%] = \frac{|\underline{V}_2|}{|\underline{V}_1|} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where $|\underline{V}_2|$ and $|\underline{V}_1|$ are the magnitudes of the negative- and positive-sequence voltage phasors, respectively, derived from the three-phase voltage measurements via the Fortescue transformation. Under perfectly balanced conditions $|\underline{V}_2| = 0$ and therefore $\text{VUF} = 0\%$. The European norm EN 50160 suggests an upper limit of 2% over 95% of the time for 10-minute samples in a given week.

Current Unbalance Ratio (CUR) Current unbalance is considerably less studied than voltage unbalance, and no single universally accepted metric exists. For this project the *Current Unbalance Ratio* (CUR), defined in [5], is adopted. CUR quantifies the largest pairwise deviation between phase currents, normalised by the total current magnitude:

$$\text{CUR} [\%] = \frac{\max(|I_A - I_B|, |I_A - I_C|, |I_B - I_C|)}{|I_A| + |I_B| + |I_C|} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where I_A , I_B , and I_C are the real-valued scalar phase currents, and the denominator is the sum of their absolute values. The numerator captures the worst-case inter-phase deviation, making the metric sensitive to the most unbalanced phase pair rather than an average imbalance. CUR equals 0% when all three phase currents are identical and reaches 100% in the extreme case where current flows in only one phase.

Figure 4: Dual axis plot of the VUF and CUR values for a substation, over the time series

Cable Loading and Thermal Capacity In addition to the total (average) current, the thermal capacity of a cable is governed by the phase carrying the highest current. Given the per-phase currents I_A , I_B , I_C at each timestep t and the rated current capacity I_{rated} of the cable, the instantaneous cable loading is defined as:

$$L(t) [\%] = \frac{\max(I_A(t), I_B(t), I_C(t))}{I_{\text{rated}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

To obtain a robust, planning-relevant summary over the full measurement period, the *peak loading* of a cable is taken as the 99th percentile of $L(t)$ across all timesteps:

$$L_{99} = P_{99}[L(t)] \quad (4)$$

Using the 99th percentile rather than the absolute maximum reduces sensitivity to momentary spikes and measurement noise, while still capturing near-worst-case operating conditions relevant for network planning. The *capacity headroom* is then the remaining margin below the rated capacity:

$$H [\%] = 100 - L_{99} \quad (5)$$

Capacity Headroom Improvement from Rebalancing To isolate the fraction of loading that is attributable purely to phase imbalance, the unbalanced power flow is compared against a *balanced* power flow in which the total three-phase power at each bus and timestep is redistributed equally across the three phases. This balanced scenario represents the theoretical optimum achievable if load allocation were perfectly balanced, without changing the total consumed power.

The *headroom improvement* ΔH for a given cable is defined as the difference between the 99th-percentile loading of the balanced case and that of the unbalanced case:

$$\Delta H [\%] = L_{99}^{\text{unbal}} - L_{99}^{\text{bal}} \quad (6)$$

A positive ΔH indicates that the existing imbalance is consuming headroom that could be recovered through rebalancing. Aggregating ΔH across all cables provides a network-wide picture of where imbalance most constrains thermal capacity.

Power Loss Improvement from Rebalancing Three-phase cable losses are computed by the power flow solver (PandaPower) for both the unbalanced and balanced scenarios. The improvement in active power losses is expressed as the mean difference in per-cable losses between the two scenarios over the entire time series:

$$\Delta P_{\text{loss}} [\text{kWh}] = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left(P_{\text{loss}}^{\text{unbal}}(t) - P_{\text{loss}}^{\text{bal}}(t) \right) \quad (7)$$

where T is the number of timesteps in the measurement period. Summing ΔP_{loss} over all cables gives the estimated total network-level energy that could be saved through load rebalancing.

Exceedance Curves The CUR time series at a given bus or line is summarised using an *exceedance curve*: the complementary cumulative distribution of the metric over the study period. For a given CUR threshold x on the horizontal axis, the vertical axis reports the percentage of 15-minute intervals during which the CUR equals or exceeds that value:

$$E(x) = P[\text{CUR}(t) \geq x] = 1 - F_{\text{CUR}}(x) \quad (8)$$

where $F_{\text{CUR}}(x)$ is the empirical cumulative distribution function of the CUR time series, estimated from the discrete observations as the fraction of intervals satisfying $\text{CUR}(t) \geq x$. The curve provides a compact overview of how frequently different levels of imbalance occur on a given node, and is generally the best way to visually compare current unbalance problems across buses or nodes.

Confusion Matrices for Imbalance Distribution To jointly visualise the *severity* and *duration* distribution of VUF and CUR, a two-dimensional matrix is used where one axis represents discrete severity bins and the other represents the duration of consecutive imbalance events. The severity bins partition the CUR range into five levels: very low ($< 20\%$), low ($[20, 40)\%$), moderate ($[40, 60)\%$), elevated ($[60, 80)\%$), and very high ($> 80\%$). The duration axis categorises consecutive episodes by their length: short (< 15 min), medium ($[15, 30)$ min), long ($[30 \text{ min}, 1 \text{ h})$), very long ($[1, 6)$ h), and sustained (> 6 h). Each cell of the matrix contains the count of events falling in the corresponding severity–duration combination.

To make patterns comparable across buses with different total numbers of events, the matrix is normalised using a doubly-stochastic (Sinkhorn) normalisation, which iteratively rescales rows and columns until every row sum and every column sum equals unity. This normalisation means that each cell reflects the joint relative weight of that severity–duration combination, corrected for marginal differences, so that high-magnitude cells indicate combinations that are simultaneously over-represented along both axes. The resulting matrix is displayed as a heatmap, enabling direct visual comparison of imbalance patterns across assets or time periods.

2.2.3 Phase Imbalance Analyser

As most data is already calculated per bus and line in the phase imbalance profiler, the phase imbalance analyser aggregates the data from the phase imbalance Profiler on different topology levels, eg, feeder, transformers, or zip code. This data is then shown in tabular format as seen in D3.1 [2]. This data app is therefore much simpler than the previous phase imbalance profiler, with onlook to making them work together as described in D4.1 [3]. Therefore, this data app has no meaningful algorithm or topology to describe other than what is outlined here

Approach The phase Imbalance profiler is a collection of analysis tools creating imbalance metrics and figures in parallel for the diagnostics of phase imbalance for buses and lines for substations.

Limitations and takeaways: The phase of cause is using the results of the Power flow tool, so the same precautions of the power flow tool also apply to the results of the phase imbalance profiler. An additional precaution should be taken to the calculation of capacity and power loss improvement as an ideal state is simulated, which most likely cannot be reached in practice. The general model provides a high degree of insight into the inner workings of the phase imbalance in the grid and can give insight into both operators and developers.

2.3 Load type detection and characterisation

2.3.1 EV charging detection

To detect electric vehicle (EV) charging events, a heuristic-driven pattern recognition framework was deployed on three-phase active power consumption time-series data sampled at 15-minute intervals.

Methodology

- **Pattern Recognition:**

The core detection is based on recognizing characteristic EV charging patterns in active power consumption (as shown in Figure 5): a rapid step increase in power, followed by a sustained high-power plateau, and a distinct power drop at the end of the charging session.

Figure 5: EV charging pattern detection logic illustrative overview.

The identification of charging events is based on typical residential EV charging power levels. Minimum charging currents (around 6 A per phase) correspond to approximately 1.4 kW, while common operating levels (16-32 A) result in power increases of 3.7 to 7.4 kW. Accordingly, a charging start is defined as a rapid increase in active power from 3.0 to 7.5 kW per phase. A corresponding decrease of at least 3 kW is required to confirm the end of the session, ensuring that only complete charging cycles are captured.

To improve robustness against slow ramping of starting and finishing the charging sessions, and timing mismatches between the physical event and its recording, the detection is based on a lagged power difference (difference between current measurement and the one before the previous measurement, or in other words, power change within 30 minutes):

$$dP_t = P_t - P_{t-2}. \tag{9}$$

This approach reduces sensitivity to slow variations and prioritizes reliable identification of charging events over precise timing. A candidate charging session is therefore registered when the start and end conditions are both satisfied.

Once a candidate session is bracketed between a start and end timestep, it must pass duration and localized stability constraints to be classified as a valid sustained charging session:

1. *Duration filter*: The candidate session length must be at least 2 hours to be considered as EV consumption behavior.
2. *Stability filter*: The standard deviation of the active power during the plateau (σ_{session}) is evaluated against the baseline noise of a pre-charging window (σ_{base}), calculated over the 2 hours before the spike. A noise floor is enforced at 50 W. The candidate session is rejected if local volatility breaks the following:

$$\sigma_{\text{session}} > 1.5 \times \sigma_{\text{base}} \quad (10)$$

Phase usage is classified simultaneously per Smart Meter (SM). By evaluating the start spike across all three measurement channels, sessions are categorized into single-phase (1ph), two-phase (2ph), or three-phase (3ph). At the smart meter level, detections are aggregated and classified according to the highest number of phases involved (3ph > 2ph > 1ph).

- **Confidence score:**

In the absence of ground-truth EV labels, a heuristic scoring framework is applied to quantify the likelihood that a given meter actually records EV charging behavior. Points are adaptively awarded and penalized based on four criteria:

1. *Session frequency*: Frequent charging behaviors scale confidence, adding +30 points for ≥ 20 sessions, +20 points for ≥ 50 sessions, and +10 points for ≥ 100 sessions (additive increments).
2. *Average charging time*: Meters with average session start time in the usual evening or night charging window (15:00–03:00) get a +30 point bonus. To avoid issues with sessions crossing midnight, we calculate the average start time using a circular method.
3. *Phase type bonus*: Because multi-phase chargers are generally more indicative of EV charging, 3ph detections are given +20 points, 2ph +10, and 1ph +5.
4. *Heat pump penalty*: To prevent false positives from high-power thermal loads, the results are cross-referenced with external heat pump phase-propagation labels. If a registered session occurs on the exact same phases that have been classified as having a heat pump, the meter is flagged as having a potential false positive and penalized by –40 points.

The final cumulative score is shifted and normalized against the maximum theoretical score (110) into an interpretable metric bounded within $[0, 100]$, which is then segmented into deterministic qualitative tiers of EV charger presence probability at this smart meter: *Low* (0–24), *Medium* (25–50), *High* (51–75), and *Very High* (76–100).

Approach: The method is applied sequentially to each smart meter time series. Candidate charging events are first identified based on power transitions and then filtered using duration and stability criteria. Valid events are aggregated at the meter level to determine phase involvement, session frequency, and typical charging times. The results are cross-checked against heat pump classifications, and all indicators are combined to assign a final confidence score and classification for each meter.

Take-away: While the method effectively captures typical EV charging behavior, it relies on predefined thresholds and heuristic rules, and is not supported by ground-truth validation. As a result, its accuracy may be limited for evolving or atypical charging patterns. The confidence scoring framework, therefore, plays a key role in interpreting results and distinguishing robust detections from uncertain cases. In the future, the approach could be further improved by adapting the methodology or incorporating data-driven techniques, such as machine learning, to better capture changing EV charging behaviors.

2.3.2 Electric heating detection

To detect electric heating (EH) devices, both statistical and machine learning (ML) models have been used in combination, based on the thesis by Hoyer and Ammentorp [9].

Methodology

General concept: Labels for EH devices are rare, and when they exist, they are often very incomplete and do not distinguish between phases. A dataset of registered heat pumps (HPs) corresponding to the smart meters used in the project was made available (in the development case, this was the Danish Government's Building Register (BBR) [10]), and are explained in greater detail in D2.1 [8]. However, this data is based on voluntary reporting and has no phase information. To make the data useful, a statistical method to distinguish labels was created. The per-phase labels can then be used in ML models to find remaining EH devices.

Probabilistic and statistical phase-labelling: Since EH and HPs exhibit the same consumer patterns at the given meter granularity, they cannot accurately be distinguished in the detection analytics. Therefore, the algorithms described in this section focus on the detection of general EH. Per-phase electric heating labels are generated from the pool of smart meters classified with a heat pump by first disaggregating each meter's load into a base load and a thermal component by using temperature bins to identify the coldest periods as a baseline. The thermal load is then estimated using Approximate Bayesian Computation, fitting truncated normal distributions to approximate how much of the consumption is heat-driven, based on the works of [11]. Three statistical models are compared using the Bayesian Information Criterion: a constant mean, a temperature-driven model, and a time-of-day schedule model. The probability that the temperature-driven model best explains the per-phase heat pump presence is interpreted as the model's confidence.

Machine learning algorithms: Three different machine learning models are implemented, with three different use cases:

- **Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering;** for no available labels.
- **Label Propagation;** for limited labels. This case fits the best the conditions of this projects incomplete labels from BBR.
- **Logistic regression;** assuming a subset of complete labels.

On Figure 7, the process pipeline from times-series data, to per-phase EH labels to ML models into the final EH classifications, can be seen. Logistic Regression and Label Propagation utilize per-phase labels, whereas Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering does not.

Feature engineering: All 3 ML algorithms utilize features based on the time-series active power of the smart meters to extract meaningful information and significantly reduce computing. In total 54 features are considered, and can be seen in [9]. If labels are available, feature selection is available; otherwise, well-performing subsets based on the radius SM data set are available.

Individual examination: For EH phase-detection analysis, it was found advantageous to evaluate all *phases* against each other instead of *inter-smart-meter* evaluation. This is both an advantage to reduce computational power, due to large data sizes, and to simplify the models.

Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering: Using the incomplete label set, it was found that the AHC [12] using ward's distance gave the best and most consistent results, by classifying each phase as either EH or non-EH. Using AHC, however, has a problem with having a computational memory complexity of $O(N^2)$ and requiring a single linkage matrix. Therefore, classifying very large datasets becomes infeasible on most machines. Therefore, for datasets above 10.000 smart meters, K-means is recommended; the relatively worse performance is somewhat offset by scaling laws, with a computational complexity of $O(N \cdot i \cdot k)$, where i is the number of iterations and k is the number of clusters. Regardless of the clustering method, the method is set to create 2 clusters, which, with the used features and parameters, derived in [9], one cluster should be EH devices and the other non-EH devices. To automatically classify which cluster is the EH, the assumption is made that below half of the households contain EH (which is true by some margin in Denmark, even using the highest estimates [9]). If labels are used, these can be used with the metrics described below to verify the clusters, else visualisation of the time-series consumption of each cluster can be used for calibration.

Label Propagation: This model utilizes label propagation [13] to classify EH devices, assuming a subset of EH labels is available. The model works with a positive class (subset of EH labels) and a negative class, propagating to the full dataset. As it is not expected to have a confirmed non-EH label set, one is generated consisting of phases that show no meaningful temperature correlation, as these most likely do not contain EH devices, and even if they do, the relative consumption on the phase makes them less interesting. This model has some parameter configuration, but it is recommended not to change too much without knowledge of it. Like with AHC, scaling for the most accurate kernel RBF is not very good because of the computational complexity of $O(N^2)$ and requiring a single linkage matrix, so it is recommended to use RBF up to around 10,000 households, after which it becomes too slow, and KNN becomes preferred, as the amount of data evens out the difference in performance between the models.

Logistic Regression: If a subset of data with proper labels can be obtained, logistic regression [14] can be used for classifying the rest of the phases. A simple, under-fitting model has been chosen because of the general low quality of the label sets. This also makes the model perform comparably to the unsupervised and semi-supervised models, when just using a subset of the BBR labels as the training set, with the caveat that, then of course, the training set can not be classified.

Confidence score: Both Label Propagation and Logistic Regression naturally output the result in confidence, and can therefore be used to move the threshold of what is considered EH. Figures 6a and 6b show the distribution of confidence for the full radius dataset [8] for the 2 models. Here, it can be seen that Label Propagation is much more deterministic as it is much more influenced by the large feature space compared to logistic regression. This also means that the Logistic Regression is more sensitive to moving the threshold.

(a) Distribution of prediction EH labels using Label Propagation.

(b) Distribution of prediction EH labels using Logistic Regression.

Figure 6: Confidence distribution of the 2 EH-detection algorithms utilizing labels.

Figure 7: Overview of electric heating detection pipeline.

Evaluation: While a lot of configuration was done by domain knowledge, it was also necessary to have some metric for the final selection of features and parameters. For this, two guiding metrics were used: **Coverage** and **Cluster-Recall**.

Cluster-recall Uses unseen labels from BBR [10] to examine what percentage of these are classified in the EH cluster. **Coverage** is the percentage of smart meters that have at least one phase classified. These metrics can be used to get a holistic understanding of the quality of the classification, but it was also found that a **Relation score** defined as:

$$\text{Relation score} = \frac{\text{Cluster-Recall} + (1 - \text{Coverage})}{2}$$

worked well as an optimization score to find the most selective models. For a deeper explanation, see [9]

Approach: All ML algorithms exist within the same module, and are executed by specifying which method is desired to be run. The methods are run by ingesting either lists of individual smart meters, or substations. The Label Propagation and Logistic Regression needs per-phase EH-labels to be computed, and will query results from the probabilistic phase-labelling method, or run the relevant smart meters if no result exists.

Take-away: As the labels can be incomplete and not fully reliable, the results of EH cannot be considered ground truth. To properly validate the methodology, surveys should be conducted on a subset of households to acquire reliable ground truth for both EH and non-EH smart meters. It should also be noted that the features that gave the best result were mostly temperature dependent, while it was found that temporal features of EH were not properly distinguishable in a 15-minute granularity. The choices of features and some of the underlying assumptions are based on both Danish smart meter data and knowledge about the presence of EH in Denmark. If this data app is deployed in a different context, it should be considered to recalibrate the models, especially for the unsupervised model. If some kind of labels are provided, a feature selection method is provided, and the metrics can be used for further calibration. If no labels are available, visualizing the time-series consumption of the clusters can indicate whether the unsupervised clustering still holds true; otherwise, manual recalibration is necessary.

Figure 8: Example of a cabinet with prominent EH on one phase, which can be clearly seen on the active power consumption, and therefore can be used for manual configuration.

2.3.3 PV detection

To detect the presence of photovoltaic (PV) systems for smart meters, a heuristic-driven pattern recognition framework was deployed on three-phase active power export time-series data sampled at 15-minute intervals.

Methodology:

- **Export detection:** At the first step, power export identification is performed by verifying the presence of non-zero values in the smart meter active power export time series for each phase.
- **Solar irradiance:** To determine whether the power output at that point was generated by the PV system, a correlation analysis with solar irradiance was conducted. Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) measures the total amount of short-wave solar radiation received by a surface horizontal to the ground, combining both direct sunlight and diffuse sky radiation. It is one of the primary parameters used to estimate the potential electricity generation of PV systems. GHI data with one-minute resolution obtained from a weather station located at the Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark.

The correlation between exported power and solar irradiance is evaluated using the Pearson correlation coefficient, which captures linear dependence between the two signals. The analysis is conducted to daytime periods only to avoid bias from night-time values ($GHI > 10 \text{ W/m}^2$). A relatively low correlation threshold (0.2) is applied to account for spatial mismatch between the smart meter location and the weather station, as well as local effects such as shading, orientation, and installation differences. If the correlation between export and solar irradiance is observed, the smart meter is classified as having a PV system installed.

Approach: The method is applied sequentially to each smart meter.

Take-away: The framework provides a computationally efficient and scalable approach to detect unmapped PV systems using existing infrastructure data. While active power export is a strong primary indicator for residential nodes, it is insufficient on its own due to the emergence of behind-the-meter assets like stationary batteries or Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) electric vehicles, which motivates the correlation analysis as a validation step.

However, the distance between the weather station and smart meter data nodes forces the use of a low correlation threshold ($r \geq 0.2$). This may lead to false positive detections of other sources of electricity exports.

Also, systems with high levels of self-consumption could go undetected; therefore, the absence of power exports does not always indicate the absence of PV installations.

Using data from only one weather station may also fail to fully reflect local conditions, which affects the quality of the correlation.

2.3.4 Phase-asymmetric PV and storage operation (Battery interference)

To investigate whether battery storage devices operate simultaneously with phase-asymmetric PV systems, a phase-to-phase correlation analysis was conducted on smart meters with PV export detected on 1 or 2 phases.

Methodology:

- **Phase identification:** Smart meters with confirmed PV installations exporting on 1 or 2 phases were selected for further analysis (991 single-phase and 432 two-phase systems). The exporting phases are identified as PV phases, while the remaining phase(s) are treated as candidate battery import phases.
- **Correlation analysis:** For single-phase PV systems, the export signal of the PV phase is correlated separately against the import signals of each remaining phase, yielding up to two correlation values per meter. For two-phase PV systems, the export signals of the two PV phases are summed and correlated against the import signal of the single remaining phase. The Pearson correlation coefficient is computed on time steps where either export or import activity is observed. A threshold of $r \geq 0.4$ is applied to flag suspected battery operation, reflecting the expectation that battery charging does not occur consistently during every PV export period.

Figure 9: Example of phase-asymmetric behaviour at a smart meter with PV and battery interaction.

An example of such phase-asymmetric behaviour is illustrated in Figure 9. During periods of PV generation, export is observed predominantly on one phase, while simultaneous import occurs on another phase, indicating battery charging. This results in a near-zero net exchange at the aggregated level, while clear phase-level imbalance is present.

Approach: The method is applied to each smart meter independently. For each meter, the applicable correlation columns are computed based on the number of PV export phases, while non-applicable combinations are left empty. The result is a single row per smart meter indicating computed correlation values, a detection flag, and the suspected battery import phase.

Take-away: Out of 1,423 smart meters with unbalanced PV installations, less than 10 cases were identified where a battery storage device is suspected to simultaneously draw power from the grid while PV is exporting to the grid. Although the number of detected cases is small, these represent a measurable phase imbalance pattern that would remain invisible without phase-level analysis, and which poses a localised challenge for grid balance management.

The low number of detections may reflect the genuinely rare occurrence of this operational pattern, but may also be influenced by the permissive correlation threshold, inconsistent battery charging behaviour, or the limitation that three-phase PV systems are excluded from the analysis, as no remaining import phase is available for correlation.

2.4 Load profile generator

Although not included as a data app, a master's thesis by Kold and Fiehn [15] was conducted as part of the 3PhaseInsight project, with a focus on conditioned creation synthetic load profiles based on the smart meter consumption data, as described in D2.1 [8]. A key idea in this work has been to create a conditional variational auto-encoder (C-VAE) for expressing generic properties of the customer profiles, while capturing all the natural variability of the profiles. This work has been exploratory, but finds applications in research to generate artificial smart meter data for study purposes, but also in

planning, to generate consumption profiles that represent changes in consumption patterns when electrification loads are added to existing demand profiles.

To evaluate the quality of the generated user profiles, Kold & Fiehn propose a broad harness of assessment metrics, including statistical metrics of distribution and temporal structure and application-oriented metrics considering e.g. peak preservation and aggregation features.

The work evaluated multiple state-of-the-art models and introduced a new hybrid model, *GUIDED-Faraday*, which achieved the highest validation scores. The thesis concluded that, for balanced data (not per-phase), it is feasible to create usable synthetic data at the distribution level for higher-level statistical analysis, but it should not be trusted to represent smart-meter data at the household level. Yet, reproducing cross-phase dependencies for per-phase data, however, still remains a challenge with unsatisfactory validation scores.

Figure 10 illustrates the methodology using the *GUIDED-Faraday* for load profile generation, including its training and reconstruction flow. The encoder maps the consumption profile and selected encoder condition vector to a Gaussian latent representation, which is regularised using a Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) loss. The decoder follows the *GUIDE-VAE*—a novel conditional generative model that leverages user embeddings to generate user-guided data structure [16], using Pattern Dictionary based Covariance Composition (PDCC) to model correlated output variation, and the reconstruction is trained using the Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL) under the resulting Gaussian distribution. The methods also include Mean Squared Error (MSE) and quantile losses to retain Faraday’s peak- and distribution-focused behaviour. After training, a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) is fitted to the encoded latent means for synthetic generation.

Figure 10: Methodology of the load profile generation with basis of the introduced *GUIDED-Faraday* model, as presented in [15].

The resulting generated time series are daily profiles, conditioned on presence of PV (production/export), electric vehicles or heat pumps, month of year and day of week, as well as a user profile condition. Five exemplary generated profiles and real profiles are illustrated in Figure 11. It is worth noting that the imperfect match between real profiles and synthetic samples is no reliable indication of inaccuracy, since the models are meant to also capture typical variability. For a full analysis of the results, we refer to the original work in [15].

2.5 Phase connector assistance

The PhaseConnector module is a decision-support tool embedded in the 3PhaseInsight mobile application, designed to guide electricians when connecting a new heat pump (HP), electric vehicle (EV) charger, or photovoltaic (PV) system to a low-voltage (LV) feeder. Rather than exposing raw smart-meter data, the tool synthesises feeder-wide measurements and appliance detection labels into a single phase recommendation, reducing the risk of worsening phase imbalance at the point of installation. The scoring logic presented here is a simplified formulation; coincidence factors and seasonal demand

Figure 11: For illustration, the figure presents "five real samples and five synthetic samples generated by GUIDED-Faraday-CNN, together with the mean of each group. The synthetic samples were generated using the same conditions as the real samples. This figure is included as a qualitative illustration and should not be used as evidence of fidelity or utility." (quoted caption from Fig. 9.5 in [15])

variations are not considered in the current implementation.

Methodology

- Three inputs are derived from smart-meter data. Let \mathcal{F} denote the set of all smart meters on the feeder and $\phi \in \{L1, L2, L3\}$ denote a phase. The feeder phase energy share is:

$$s_{\phi}^{C1} = \frac{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{F}} E_{m,\phi}}{\sum_{\phi'} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{F}} E_{m,\phi'}} \quad (11)$$

where $E_{m,\phi}$ is the total active energy measured at meter m on phase ϕ . The same-type appliance count share is:

$$s_{\phi}^{C2} = \frac{n_{\phi}}{\sum_{\phi'} n_{\phi'}} \quad (12)$$

where n_{ϕ} is the number of appliances of the target type already connected to phase ϕ , as identified by label propagation. The household phase energy share s_{ϕ}^{C3} is defined analogously to s_{ϕ}^{C1} but restricted to the household smart meter under consideration.

- Each phase is scored against the ideal balanced share $s^* = 1/3$. For load appliances (HP, EV), a phase with lower current share scores higher, reflecting available headroom. For PV, C1 and C3 are inverted to favour the most-loaded phase and maximise self-consumption. The per-criterion scores are:

$$\text{score}_{\phi}^{C1} = \begin{cases} \max\left(0, 1 - \frac{s_{\phi}^{C1}}{s^*}\right) \times w_1 & \text{HP/EV} \\ \frac{s_{\phi}^{C1}}{s^*} \times w_1 & \text{PV} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

and equivalently for C2 (HP/EV direction only) and C3. The total score for phase ϕ is:

$$\text{score}_{\phi} = \text{score}_{\phi}^{C1} + \text{score}_{\phi}^{C2} + \text{score}_{\phi}^{C3} \quad (14)$$

with weights $w_1 = 40$, $w_2 = 30$, $w_3 = 30$, giving a maximum of 100 points. The recommended phase is $\phi^* = \arg \max_{\phi} \text{score}_{\phi}$.

Approach: C1, C2, and C3 are computed from a single shared data pass, ensuring the visualisations shown to the electrician and the recommendation scores are numerically consistent. The output is a ranked result with per-criterion scores and raw input shares, enabling the mobile UI to surface the

driving factors of any recommendation. A threshold-based decision layer maps the total score to one of three actionable labels: *proceed* (score 70–100), *conditional – smart control advised* (45–69), or *verify on site* (0–44). The weights w_1, w_2, w_3 and decision thresholds are configurable parameters, and can be adjusted to reflect DSO-specific grid policies, local feeder characteristics, or appliance penetration levels.

Take-away: The tool converts multi-source smart-meter analytics (feeder topology, appliance detection labels, and household consumption profiles) into a single actionable phase recommendation. Decision thresholds (proceed / conditional / verify on site) make the output usable by a field electrician without requiring grid analysis expertise.

3 Conclusions

This deliverable documents the algorithms underlying the data apps developed within the 3PhaseInsight project, including data preparation and quality enhancement, phase imbalance assessment and power flow analysis, and detection of significant electrification loads. It complements D3.1 [2] by explaining how the results are generated and documenting the methodological choices, algorithmic dependencies, and design trade-offs behind each app. Code-level implementation details are available in the open-source repository².

The methods used in Smart meter data preparation and quality enhancement data apps provide comprehensive methodologies for handling, validating, and correcting data for use in most other apps and to complement data pipelines. They are also relevant to implementing an open-source framework detailed in D4.1 [3] for applying the method to new data.

The Phase imbalance assessment and power flow analysis section describes methods for understanding, identifying, and quantifying phase imbalance in the low-voltage grid. The Load type detection and characterisation section presents a range of methods for identifying electrical loads such as Electric heating, PVs, and EVs, in Smart meter data with either no or limited reference labels, and also discusses the pitfalls and challenges for each case. At the same time, a novel approach to creating synthetic load profiles for the aforementioned electrical units is proposed. Lastly, a method is introduced that combines the identified load labels with the existing per-phase loading to recommend which phase a newly installed unit should connect to, thereby minimising phase imbalance.

²3PhaseInsight on Github: <https://github.com/3PhaseInsight>

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